

ON THE CONSTITUTION OF THE ALKALOID ISOLATED FROM THE BARK OF *CHLOROXYLON SWIETENIA*, D.C.

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From the matured bark of *Chloroxylon swietenia*, D.C. an alkaloid, m.p. 176-77° and a bitter crystalline substance, m.p. 186° have been isolated. The alkaloid has been proved to be identical with skimmianine, previously isolated from six *Rutaceous* species by various workers.

Chloroxylon swietenia, D.C., commonly known as Indian satin wood, is indigenous to India and it belongs to the family *Meliaceae*.

Auld (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 964) and Boorsma (*Meded S'Lands Plantent*, 1899, 31, 105, 131) isolated from the bark of this species an alkaloid, chloroxylonine, m.p. 182-183°, having the molecular formula $C_{14}H_{11}O_3N(OMe)_4$. Chloroxylonine was found to be laevorotatory and it developed dermatitis when applied to the skin (Cash, *Brit. Med. J.*, October 7, 1911). The yield of alkaloid being very poor and the method of extraction being extremely laborious, these workers did not further study its properties or determine its constitution.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to establishing the constitution of chloroxylonine. The bark of the plant was kindly supplied by Dr. K. P. Biswas, Superintendent of the Royal Botanic Garden, Sibpur, Howrah, and Mr. S. N. Bal, Curator of the Industrial Section, Indian Museum, Calcutta, to whom the authors' best thanks are due.

The method of isolation adopted in the present work was quite different from, and simpler than that used by Auld and others (*vide supra*). The bark was dried in the sun, crushed, Soxhletted with ether. An alkaloid was isolated from the ether extract by digestion with aqueous hydrochloric acid. The residual ether extract, which contained non-basic constituents, on subsequent evaporation left a bitter, crystalline substance, m.p. 186°. The nature of the alkaloid is the subject matter of the present communication.

The analytical data of the pure crystalline base and its picrate indicate the formula $C_{14}H_{13}O_3N$ which is confirmed by M.W. data. It is free from any *N*-methyl (Herzig and Meyer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 319; *Monatsh*, 1894, 15, 613; 1897, 18, 382) and methylenedioxy groups (Gaebel, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1910, 248, 207) but shows the presence of three methoxyl groups when tested by the method of Zeisel-Pregel-Viebock (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2881, 3207; *Monatsh*, 1885, 6, 989; 1886, 7, 406). No acetyl or benzoyl derivative could be prepared. Evidently the nitrogen atom is tertiary in character.

The analytical data of the base, its properties and reactions suggested that it might be identical with skimmianine (I), an alkaloid isolated from six different *Rutaceous* species, namely *Skimmia japonica*, Thunb (Honda, *Arch. Expt. Pathol. Pharm.*, 1904, 52, 83; Asahina and Inubase, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2056; Späth and Neufeld, *Ber.*, 1938, 71B, 353; Takeda, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1941, 61, 117), *Skimmia repens*, Nakai (Asahina, Ohta and Inubase, *Ber.*, 1930, 63B, 2045), *Skimmia laureola*, Hook (Chopra, Chatterjee, Dey and Ghosh, *J. Indian Med. Res.*, 1938, 26, 481), *Orixa japonica*, Thunb (Takesiso,

J. Pharm. Soc. Japan, 1939, 59, 136), *Fagara mantschurica*, Honta (Ryosuke, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1944, 61, 91) and *Fagara Coco* (Gill) Engl (Stucherts and his collaborators, *Investigaciones del Laboratorio de quimica Biologica Coroba*, Argentine, 1, 1933, 2, 1938; Deulofeu, Labriola and Murusabal, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1357). An authentic specimen of skimmianine being not available our compound was degraded to an aldehyde and an acid, the latter being further subjected to decarboxylation. The properties of these compounds were compared with the corresponding products obtained from skimmianine. These are presented in Table I. It will be seen from the data that the alkaloid isolated by us from *C. swietenia* is most probably identical with skimmianine (I).

TABLE I

	Alkaloid from	
	<i>C. swietenia</i> .	Skimmianine.
M.p.	176-77°	176°
Mol. formula	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N
Optical activity	Nil	Nil
Picrate		
M.p.	197-98° (decomp.)	195-97° (decomp.)
Mol. formula	(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N).C ₆ H ₅ O ₇ N ₃	(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N).C ₆ H ₅ O ₇ N ₃
Chloroplatinate		
Mol. of formula	(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N) ₂ .H ₂ PtCl ₆	(C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N) ₂ .H ₂ PtCl ₆
M.p.	Chars when heated above 200° but does not melt	Not recorded
Degradation products		
(a) Aldehyde (Formula II)		
M.p.	238° (decomp.)	238° (decomp.)
Mol. formula	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₂ N(OMe) ₃	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₂ N(OMe) ₃ (Skimmianal)
Phenylhydrazone of (a)		
M.p.	210° (decomp.)	210° (decomp.)
Mol. formula	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃
(b) Acid (Formula III)		
M.p.	248° (decomp.)	248° (decomp.)
Mol. formula	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₆ N	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₆ N (Skimmianic acid)
(c) Decarboxylation product of the acid (b) (Formula IV)		
M.p.	250° (decomp.)	250° (decomp.)
Mol. formula	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N
(d) Nitroso derivative of (c)		
M.p.	246° (decomp.)	246° (decomp.)

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Isolation of Skimmiamine.—The sun-dried, matured bark of *Chloroxylon swietenia* (4 kg.) was powdered in a mortar and sieved. The fine powder was extracted with ether (3 litres) for 48 hours in a soxhlet. The deep brown ethereal extract was concentrated to 500 c.c. and digested with 0.1% hydrochloric acid (300 c.c., in 5 instalments) when the base completely passed into the acid layer (A) as tested with Dragendorff's reagent. The ethereal solution was evaporated to a small bulk (100 c.c.) and kept in the frigidaire when it deposited a bitter crystalline substance (B) (4.0 g., yield 0.1 %), m.p. 186°. This will be the subject matter of a future communication.

The acid digest (A ; *vide supra*) was cooled in ice and carefully basified with aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The precipitate was vigorously shaken up with ether thrice (in 100 c.c. portions) when the base passed into the ether layer. The pale yellow ether extract was twice washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled. The residue was an oil which slowly solidified to a crystalline mass (2.0 g., yield 0.05%). This was successively crystallised from ethyl acetate, alcohol and acetone in glistening colourless prisms till the m.p. became constant at 176°. There was no loss in weight when the crystals were dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100°.

[Found : C, 65.06 ; H, 4.92 ; N, 5.31 ; OMe, 35.62 ; M. W. (by chloroplatinate method), 266, 268. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 64.86 ; H, 5.02 ; N, 5.40 ; OMe, 35.96 per cent. M.W. 259].

The base is optically inactive and its solution in alcohol is neutral to litmus. Being a weak base, it does not form stable salts with mineral acids and can be quantitatively precipitated from its acid solution by sodium bicarbonate. The base does not contain any water of crystallisation and its alcoholic solution does not produce any colouration with ferric chloride. Its behaviour towards various reagents is recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Reagent	Colour.
1. Concentrated H_2SO_4	Pale yellow solution with a green fluorescence.
2. Concentrated HNO_3	Orange red changing to red.
3. Erdman's reagent	Pale yellow, changing to red, finally to orange red.
4. Frohde's reagent	Pale yellow changing to olive green after a day.
5. Mandelin's reagent	Dirty yellow changing to olive green and finally to emerald green.

The base gives an orange precipitate with potassium bismuth iodide, a white precipitate with Meyer's reagent, a chocolate brown precipitate with a solution of iodine in potassium iodide and a crystalline yellow precipitate with picric acid, and an orange crystalline compound with chloroplatinic acid.

The base is readily soluble in acetone, fairly in chloroform, sparingly in ethyl acetate, benzene and ether, and insoluble in petroleum ether and water. The alkaloid readily dissolves in aqueous hydrochloric, nitric, and sulphuric acids but the corresponding salts could not be isolated in the pure state.

Picrate of the Base.—The picrate of the base was prepared by adding an ethereal solution of picric acid to an ethereal solution of the base (0.15 g.). The yellow precipitate was collected, washed with ether and a little cold alcohol. It crystallised from alcohol in lustrous shining yellow silky needles (0.12 g.), m.p. 197-98° (decomp.). [Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100° : C, 49.45; H, 3.25; N, 11.78. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N.C_6H_2(OH)(NO_2)_3$ requires C, 49.18; H, 3.28; N, 11.48 per cent].

Chloroplatinate.—It was readily prepared by adding an excess of platinum chloride solution (5%) to a solution of the base in hydrochloric acid. The orange crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed with water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid. It was purified by three crystallisations from boiling water, when orange yellow plates were obtained. The chloroplatinate did not melt but charred when heated above 200°. Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 110° : Pt, 20.7, 20.6. $(C_{14}H_{13}O_4N)_2.H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 21.01 per cent].

Oxidation with Potassium Permanganate.—Oxidation by means of potassium permanganate was carried out by the method of Asahina (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2056). The solution of the base (0.5 g.) in acetone (30 c.c.) was gently refluxed on a water-bath and a neutral solution of potassium permanganate in acetone (1.0 g. in 20 c.c. acetone) was added in small portions. The solution was then refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled and filtered (filtrate *a*). The brown precipitate of manganese dioxide (residue *b*) separating was thoroughly washed with boiling acetone and the washings were added to the filtrate (*a*).

Isolation of Skimmianine Aldehyde (Skimmianal).—The combined pale yellow filtrates were freed from the solvent and the residue was digested with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and filtered. The filtrate (*c*) and the residue (*b*) (*vide supra*) were subsequently worked up for the acid (*vide infra*). The residue insoluble in sodium bicarbonate was twice crystallised from acetone. The shining yellow needles (0.20 g.) thus, obtained, melted at 238° (decomp.). (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100° : C, 59.50; H, 4.86; N, 5.51; OMe, 35.12. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 59.31; H, 4.94; N, 5.32; OMe, 35.36 per cent).

Phenylhydrazone of the Aldehyde.—The alcoholic solution of the aldehyde (0.15 g.) was refluxed with freshly distilled phenylhydrazine (0.4 g.) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 c.c.). The product was poured into cold water and the resulting precipitate crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles (0.1 g.) melting at 210° (decomp.). On further crystallisation from alcohol and other solvents there was no rise in the m.p. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100° : N, 12.00. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4N_2$ requires N, 11.93 per cent).

Isolation of Skimmianine Acid (Skimmianic acid).—The mixture of manganese dioxide residue (*b*) and the sodium bicarbonate filtrate (*c*) (*vide supra*) was thoroughly digested with more sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered. The filtrate (50 c.c.) was cooled in ice, acidified with hydrochloric acid (congo red). The flocculent precipitate was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless needles (0.12 g.), m.p. 248° (decomp.). (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100° : C, 55.63; H, 4.71; N, 4.99; OMe, 33.51. $C_{13}H_{13}O_6N$ requires C, 55.91; H, 4.66; N, 5.02; OMe, 33.33 per cent).

Decarboxylation of the Acid.—The acid (0.15 g.) was suspended in dilute hydrochloric acid in water (20 c.c.) and refluxed. After 4 hours the acid completely dissolved with evolution of carbon dioxide. On concentrating the light pink solution (to 5 c.c.) colourless crystals separated (0.05 g.). These were collected and crystallised from alcohol. The needles melted at 250° (decomp.). It readily dissolves in alkali and alkali carbonates. (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100°: C, 58.02; H, 4.86; N, 6.41; OMe, 27.85. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 59.73; H, 4.98; N, 6.33; OMe, 28.05 per cent).

Nitroso derivative of the Decarboxylation Product.—The decarboxylation product (0.03 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide (1 c.c.) and the calculated amount of sodium nitrite (0.06 g.) was added to the solution. The mixture was dropped to a cooled solution of 10% sulphuric acid with shaking. The reddish precipitate, thus obtained, was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from acetic acid in red needles, m.p. 246° (decomp.). (Found in a sample dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 3 hours at 100°: N, 11.10. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10.91 per cent).

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